

SUPPRESSION OF DELAMINATION CRACK FOR THE FOAM CORE SANDWICH PANEL JOINT

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Keywords: *sandwich panel, foam core, joint, delamination crack*

1 Introduction

In order to reduce the structural weight and part count, fundamental researches on the application of co-cured CFRP face plates/ foamed plastic core sandwich panel to aircraft structure have been conducted. In these researches, Hirose *et al.*[1] reported that, if co-cured CFRP face/ foam core sandwich panels were applied to aircraft structure, especially to the complexly curved surface portion such as nose fuselage structures, structural weight and part count could be significantly reduced. In this application, panel joints are inevitable structural elements because of the restriction of production facilities. For the configuration of the joint, a tapered end-closure type joint as shown in Fig.1(a) was selected and studied by Hirose *et al.*[2]. In this type of the joint, the sandwich panel is tapered to form the solid laminate of two face plates near the joint portion and two panels to be joined are mechanically fastened at the solid laminate portions with a splice plate. However, it was reported that the delamination crack initiating from tapered core end and propagating through the interface between two face plates as shown in Fig.1(b) was observed as an initial failure mode at much lower tensile load compared to the final failure load.

If design parameters such as angle of tapered panel portion are adequately selected, initial failure could be restrained. In this study, the effect of the angle of tapered panel portion on the load level of delamination crack initiation (or initial crack propagation) is experimentally and analytically investigated and how to design the taper angle to suppress the initial failure is discussed.

2 Sandwich panel joint tensile test

To evaluate the effect of the taper angle on the initial failure load, tensile tests were conducted using the test pieces with the taper angles of 10deg, 20deg and 30deg. Dimensions of the test piece are

shown in Fig.2 and Fig.3. Face plates of sandwich panel consisted of 16-ply graphite/epoxy twill weave fabric composite (UT500/#135) laminates with nominal thickness of 6.24 mm. The ply orientations of the face laminate were $[\{(+45,-45)/(0,90)\}_4]_{sym}$. Polyether imide (PEI) foam constituted the core. The thickness of the core was 34 mm. Resin films with thickness of 0.254 mm were inserted between the face laminate and the foam core. These resin films were extended by 5 mm to the solid laminate portion from the tapered core end. The thickness of the aluminum splice plate was 10 mm. The splice plate was installed by titanium bolts with the diameter of 7.92 mm and the spacing of 32 mm.

Twelve strain gauges were attached to each test piece to monitor strain variations during the tensile test. Placements of strain gauges are shown in Fig.4. Strain gauges A and B were placed at 250 mm from the edge of solid laminate portion to monitor the strain variations on the top and the bottom surfaces of flat sandwich panel portion (strain gauges A and B were placed at the tapered panel portion for the test piece with taper angle of 10deg because there was no flat sandwich panel portion). To monitor the strain variation on the top surface of the tapered panel portion, strain gauge C was placed at 109 mm (129 mm, 179.5 mm) from the edge of solid laminate portion for the 30 deg (20 deg, 10 deg) test pieces. Strain gauges D, F, H, I were placed at 83 mm from the edge of solid laminate portion to monitor the strain variations on the top and the bottom surfaces near the tapered core end. Strain gauges E, J, K, L were also placed at 83mm from the edge of solid laminate portion, however, these were attached on the edge face near the tapered core end and utilized to measure the strain along the thickness direction. These strain gauges E, J, K, L were considered to be sensitive to the delamination crack initiation from the tapered core end. Strain gauge G was used to monitor the strain at the center of splice plate.

Three test pieces for each taper angle (total nine test pieces) were prepared. Fig.5 shows the photographs of the test pieces. Tensile tests were performed using universal test machine (SHIMADZU Autograph AG-I) with loading capacity of 50 kN at the crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. Experimental setup is shown in Fig.6. At both ends of the test piece, ten CFRP plies were added to the top and the bottom face plates and potting compound was used to fill the portion between the two face plates in order to prevent the failure of the test piece due to the application of tensile load. Loading apparatus attached to the lower end of the specimen was fixed to the base of the test machine. On the other hand, the upper loading apparatus was installed to the test machine crosshead through the universal joint (not shown in Fig.6). Thus, constraint conditions on the lower and upper ends of the test piece were slightly different.

During the test, strain variation (especially strain variation of gauges E, J, K, L which are installed on the edge face near the tapered core end) were carefully monitored and the delamination crack initiation and propagation from the core end to the solid laminate portion were visually inspected using a microscope. When an abnormal strain variation was observed, tensile load was kept temporarily and detail inspection of the crack initiation was conducted. These procedures were repeated until the crack initiation and propagation were confirmed. In this study, the tensile load, when the delamination crack which initiated from tapered core end, propagated by 5mm through the interface between two resin films and extended into the solid laminate portion was observed, is defined as an initial failure load.

3 Delamination fracture toughness evaluation test

In order to investigate the delamination crack initiation and propagation behavior in the tapered end-closure type joint based on the fracture mechanics, the delamination fracture toughness of the constituent material needs to be evaluated. Through the finite element analysis described later, it was clarified that the mode II component was dominant in the energy release rate for the delamination crack discussed in this study. Thus the mode II delamination fracture toughness of the CFRP face plate was evaluated through the end notched flexure (ENF) test.

Fig.7 shows the dimensions of the specimen used in the ENF test. Length and width of specimen was 140 mm and 20 mm. In order to introduce a starter delamination crack into the specimen, a release film (Kapton film) with the thickness of 12.5 μm was inserted at the middle plane of the specimen in 40 mm length portion from the edge of the specimen. Span between two support fixtures was set to be 100 mm and the distance between the tip of the release film and the support fixture on the cracked side was set to be 20 mm. Test specimen consisted of 16-ply graphite/epoxy twill weave fabric composite (UT500/#135) and cured in the same condition as that of the joint test piece. Stacking sequence of the ENF test specimen is $(0,90)_8/F/(0,90)_8$ where “F” means the starter release film. Nominal thickness of the specimen was 6.08 mm.

ENF tests are conducted using universal test machine (SHIMADZU Autograph AGS-G) with loading capacity of 5 kN at the crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. Experimental setup is shown in Fig.8.

Procedures to evaluate the mode II delamination fracture toughness from the ENF test data were based on the Japanese Industrial Standards (JIS-K7086) [3]. Load-displacement data obtained from ENF tests were used in the equations (1) and (2) to evaluate the mode II delamination fracture toughness G_{IIc} .

$$a_1 = \left[\frac{C_1}{C_0} a_0^3 + \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{C_1}{C_0} - 1 \right) L^3 \right]^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (1)$$

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{9 a_1^2 P_C^2 C_1}{2B(2L^3 + 3a_1^3)} \quad (2)$$

where

a_0 : starter crack length

P_C : critical load

C_0 : loading point compliance in initial elastic portion

C_1 : loading point compliance at critical load

a_1 : estimated crack length at critical load

L : half span between two support points

B : width of specimen

4 Finite element analysis

Two dimensional finite element models of the joint test pieces with taper angle of 10deg, 20deg and 30deg were prepared to estimate the load when the initial failure occurred. Fig.9 shows the model of the

joint with the taper angle of 30deg. Face plates, core, resin films and splice plate were modeled using 4-node plane elements. Beam elements were utilized to model the fastener bolts (Fig.9(a) and (b)). To simulate the tensile load application to the test piece through the universal joint, a master node is placed on the rotational axis of the universal joint and rigid elements were created between the master node and the nodes on one end of the test piece. Then, tensile load was applied to the master node of the rigid elements (Fig.9(c)). The close-up of the finite element model around the tapered core end is also shown in Fig.9(d) and (e). An initial delamination crack which initiated from tapered core end, propagated through interface between two resin films by 5 mm and extended into the solid laminate portion with the length of 2 mm was included in the analysis model. The energy release rate of the initial delamination crack was calculated utilizing the virtual crack closure method. Geometric nonlinear effect was included in the analysis and mode components of the energy release rate were defined based on the deformed shape around the crack tip. A new coordinate system $x'-y'$ were defined using the deformed position of nodes near the crack tip as shown in Fig.10, where the coordinate x' was aligned to the dotted straight line which passes through the node $i+1$ and the point midway between node i and node i' . And mode I and mode II energy release rates were calculated based on the new coordinate system $x'-y'$ using the equations

$$G_I = \frac{1}{2\Delta a} F_{y'}^{(i+1)} (u_{y'}^{(i')} - u_{y'}^{(i)}) \quad (3)$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{1}{2\Delta a} F_{x'}^{(i+1)} (u_{x'}^{(i')} - u_{x'}^{(i)}) \quad (4)$$

$$G = G_I + G_{II} \quad (5)$$

where $F_{x'}$ and $F_{y'}$ are components of nodal force and $u_{x'}$ and $u_{y'}$ are components of nodal displacement in the new coordinate system. Superscripts $(i+1)$, (i) and (i') represent the related nodes described in Fig.10.

Finite element analysis was conducted using MSC. Marc 2008 r1. Mechanical properties of constituent materials used in the analysis are shown in Table 1 and 2. In tensile tests of the joint test piece, plastic deformation of the aluminum splice plate was observed. Therefore, material behavior of the aluminum splice plate was assumed to be elastic perfectly plastic with the yield stress of $\sigma_y = 155$ MPa.

After conducting the analysis, the initial failure load of the panel joint was estimated as the load when the energy release rate of the initial crack included in the analysis model reached its critical value. In this estimation, the delamination fracture toughness which was experimentally evaluated through the procedures described in Sec 3 was employed as the critical energy release rate.

5 Results

5.1 Sandwich panel joint tensile test result

Fig.11 shows the strain variation with the tensile load for the test piece with taper angle of 20deg (typical one test result is shown). Symbols shown in Fig.11 such as A, B, etc. identify the strain measuring points which are shown in Fig.4. As the tensile load increased, the strain of gauges D and H, which were attached to the top face near the tapered core end, increased. While, strains of gauges F and I, which were attached to the bottom face, decreased (compressive strains increased). These strain variations indicate that the bending deformation, in which the bottom surface became concave surface, occurred near the tapered core end.

Fig.11 also shows that the strain of gauges E, J, K and L, which are attached on the edge face near the tapered core end, rapidly increased when the tensile load increased over 19 kN. These abnormal strain variations indicate the sign of delamination crack initiation at the tapered core end. After abnormal strain variation occurred, the edge face of the test piece was visually inspected to find the delamination crack initiation. When the tensile load increased to 21.6 kN, a crack which initiated from tapered core end, propagated through the interface between two resin films by 5mm and extended into the solid laminate portion was observed. Fig.12(a) shows the photograph of the initial delamination crack. In the experiments, the load when the crack extension into the solid laminate portion was observed was defined as the initial failure load (In this test piece, the initial failure load was 21.6 kN). As the tensile load increased over the initial failure load, the crack propagated through the interface between two face plates. Fig.12(b) shows this delamination crack when the tensile load increased to 32.0 kN.

Initial failure load of nine test pieces (three test pieces for each taper angle) are summarized in Table 3. These test results show that the initial failure load increases if the taper angle decreases and thus

indicate that the smaller taper angle is preferred to suppress the initial failure which occurs at the tapered core end.

5.2 Delamination fracture toughness evaluation test result

Fig.13 shows load -loading point displacement curves obtained from ENF tests of three specimens. Table 4 summarizes the data obtained from these curves and Table 5 shows the evaluated mode II delamination fracture toughness G_{IIc} . When estimating the initial failure load of the panel joint test piece through the finite element analysis, mode II delamination fracture toughness of $G_{IIc}= 2.08$ kJ/m² (mean value shown in Table 5) was utilized as the critical energy release rate.

5.3 Finite element analysis result

In order to validate the finite element model of the test piece, numerically calculated strains were compared with experimentally measured strains. Fig.14(a), 14(b) and 14(c) show the strains at measuring point A, B, C, D and F (see Fig.4) for the test piece with taper angle 10deg, 20deg and 30deg respectively when the tensile load is 15 kN. The mean value of three test pieces' results is shown with diamond marker and the numerical result is shown with circle marker. Numerical results show good agreement with experimental results and the validity of the finite element model is confirmed.

Fig.15 shows the relations between the total energy release rate of delamination crack included in the finite element model (see Fig.9(e)) and the tensile load for the taper angle of 10deg, 20deg and 30deg. Fig.15 shows that, at the same tensile load level, the total energy release rate decreases as the taper angle decreases. In other words, in order to obtain the same total energy release rate, panel joint with smaller taper angle needs higher tensile load. Related to the numerical results shown in Fig.15, Table 6 presents the mode I and mode II components of the energy release rate for the case of taper angle 30deg. Table 6 shows the mode I ratio to the total energy release rates is less than 3 % in the load level from 0 to 30 kN. In the case of taper angle 10deg and 20deg, the mode I ratio is also less than 3% in the same load level. Therefore, the delamination crack can be considered to be in pure mode II condition.

Assuming the critical energy release rate to be the mode II fracture toughness $G_{IIc}= 2.55$ kJ/m², which was obtained from the ENF test described in Sec 5.2,

tensile loads at which the initial crack included in the model will propagate can be calculated. The tensile load obtained through this procedure is defined as estimated initial failure load in this paper. Estimated initial failure loads are presented along with the experimental results in Table 7. Both analytical estimations and experimental results show that the initial failure load increases as the taper angle decreases. And the initial failure load can be well evaluated through the finite element analysis, though there are some amounts of overestimation for the test piece with 30deg taper angle.

6 Conclusions

For the tapered end-closure type sandwich panel joint, it is clarified through the experimental and analytical investigations that the smaller angle of tapered panel portion is preferred to suppress the initial failure which occurs at the tapered core end. Therefore, to design the joints, the taper angle should be sufficiently small such that the crack initiation and propagation at the tapered core end do not occur before other modes of failure.

References

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Fig.1 Configurations of a tapered end-closure type joint.

Fig.4 Twelve strain measuring points on the test piece.

Fig.2 Dimensions of the test piece.

Fig.5 Photographs of the test pieces.

Fig.3 Detail dimensions of the test piece.

Fig.6 Panel joint tensile test setup.

Symbols in Fig.7	Description	Dimension [mm]
l	Specimen length	140
B	Specimen width	20
a_0	Starter crack length	20
d	Starter film insert length	40
L	Half span between two support points	50
r_1	Radius of loading apparatus	5
r_2	Radius of support fixture	5

Fig.7 ENF test specimen.

Fig.8 ENF test setup.

(a) Model of test piece

(b) Model of solid laminate portion

(c) Tensile load application through rigid element

(d) Model near the tapered core end

(e) Initial delamination crack

Fig.9 Finite element model of the joint test piece.

Fig.10 Coordinate system $x'-y'$ defined using the deformed position of nodes near the crack tip.

(a) Tensile load = 21.6 kN

(b) Tensile load = 32.0 kN

Fig.12 Photographs of a delamination crack (for the case of taper angle 20deg).

Fig.11 Strain variations with tensile load (for the case of taper angle 20deg).

Fig.13 Load vs. displacement curves obtained from ENF test.

Fig.14 Calculated and measured strains on the panel joint test pieces at tensile load of 15kN.

Fig.15 Energy release rate variation with tensile load obtained from finite element analysis.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of constituent plies of CFRP face plates[2]

	CFRP (0,90) RC=35%	CFRP (+45,-45) RC=35%	CFRP (0,90) RC=45%	CFRP (+45,-45) RC=45%
E_{11} [GPa]	66.4	15.2	54.9	12.5
E_{22} [GPa]	8.61	8.61	8.61	8.61
E_{33} [GPa]	66.4	15.2	54.9	12.5
ν_{12}	0.331	0.0756	0.331	0.0755
ν_{23}	0.0429	0.0429	0.0519	0.0519
ν_{31}	0.0510	0.783	0.0510	0.784
G_{12} [GPa]	4.23	4.23	4.23	4.23
G_{23} [GPa]	4.23	4.23	4.23	4.23
G_{31} [GPa]	4.25	31.6	3.51	26.1

1: In-plane longitudinal direction

2: Thickness direction

Note: The resin content (RC) of two plies which are adjacent to the foam core was increased from 35% to 45%

Table 2 Mechanical properties of constituent materials[2,4]

	PEI foam core	Resin film	Al splice plate	Ti bolt
E [GPa]	0.037	2.76	70.0	116
ν	0.321	0.335	0.33	0.31

Table 3 Initial failure load obtained from tensile tests

Taper angle [deg]	No.	Initial failure load [kN]	
10	#1	28.2	mean 28.0
	#2	27.4	
	#3	28.5	
20	#1	21.6	mean 21.6
	#2	21.6	
	#3	21.6	
30	#1	17.1	mean 17.6
	#2	18.1	
	-3	17.7	

Table 7 Initial failure load

Taper angle [deg]	Initial failure load [kN]	
	Experiment	Analytical estimation
10	28.0	27.3
20	21.6	21.9
30	17.6	19.8

Table 4 Data obtained from ENF test and used in equation (2)

Specimen	P_C [kN]	C_0 [mm/kN]	C_1 [mm/kN]	a_1 [mm]
#1	2.14	1.16	1.22	23.4
#2	2.04	1.16	1.21	22.8
#3	1.87	1.16	1.22	23.4

Table 5 Mode II fracture toughness G_{IIc}

Specimen	G_{IIc} [kJ/m ²]	
#1	2.37	mean 2.08
#2	2.06	
#3	1.81	

Table 6 Mode components of energy release rate for taper angle 30deg

Load [kN]	G_I [kJ/m ²]	G_{II} [kJ/m ²]	G_{total} [kJ/m ²]	G_I/G_{total} [%]
5	0.003	0.117	0.120	2.47
10	0.012	0.436	0.448	2.75
15	0.030	1.000	1.030	2.92
20	0.061	2.079	2.140	2.87
25	0.108	3.707	3.815	2.84
30	0.170	5.761	5.931	2.86